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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPT OF ENTREPRENEURSH

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Abstract. This article discusses the theoretical foundations and interpretation of the development of the concept of entrepreneurship. Also, conclusions are presented on the development of the concept of entrepreneurship.

Key words. Entrepreneurship, capital, factor, theory, approach.

Entrepreneurship is considered an important and multifaceted category in economic sciences, and its essence is closely linked with the development of society, market relations, and production methods. In this regard, increasing market competition, integration processes, and dynamic changes in the socio-economic environment are being observed, which significantly complicate the activities of enterprises. Among the specific characteristics of enterprise activities are a considerable reduction in the production cycle and a low turnover of capital. This necessitates clarifying theoretical principles, improving existing ones, and forming new approaches to ensure well-grounded management of the development process of state entities, which is also important for other sectors of the national economy.

In this context, the development of entrepreneurship is considered the main objective as the primary driving force toward civilized market relations. This substantiates the necessity of creating sufficient conditions to activate all forms of entrepreneurial activity during the reform process. Each area of entrepreneurship (small, medium, and large business) has its own specific features, advantages, and significance, providing important opportunities for restoring the national economy and its productive forces.

In early economic doctrines, entrepreneurial activity was mainly interpreted as a process of risk-taking and profit generation. In particular, R. Cantillon defined the entrepreneur as a person who assumes risk. The theory of entrepreneurship emerged in the 18th century, and the term “entrepreneurship” was first introduced into economic science by the English economist R. Cantillon. He regarded entrepreneurship as a distinct type of innovative activity involving risk. The concept of entrepreneurship was associated with a person who undertakes the risk related to organizing new production and implementing new ideas, characterized by bearing unpaid costs for their own benefit.

A. Smith viewed entrepreneurship as a means of effectively mobilizing capital. That is, Smith defined the entrepreneur as a property owner who takes economic risks to implement a specific commercial idea and earn profit. According to him, the entrepreneur plans, organizes production, and analyzes its results. In subsequent periods, the concept of entrepreneurship expanded further, particularly through J.B. Say, who substantiated it as an activity that combines factors of production. Thus, the next stage in analyzing entrepreneurial activity was carried out by the prominent French economist J.B. Say, who considered entrepreneurship as a rational and, at the same time, creative activity aimed at combining production factors.

In the 20th century, the Austrian School economist Joseph Schumpeter made a significant contribution to entrepreneurship theory. He accurately formulated the most characteristic features of the entrepreneur and described their main functions as producing new goods or new qualities of existing goods, developing new markets, obtaining new sources of raw materials or semi-finished products, introducing new production methods, and carrying out corresponding reorganizations. According to Schumpeter, in order to constantly search for new ways of combining resources, an entrepreneur must possess willpower and ability, the capacity to identify decisive moments in activity and perceive them realistically, the social strength to overcome resistance and “swim against the current,” as well as the capacity to influence others through the results of success, moral freedom, strength, and energy expenditure. Schumpeter evaluated entrepreneurship as the driving force of economic development and linked it to innovations, new products, technologies, and market introductions. Thus, entrepreneurship theory has evolved through classical, neoclassical, and institutional approaches.

Based on the above considerations, the theory of entrepreneurship has been summarized and presented in a separate table reflecting the viewpoints of several scholars from foreign countries, the CIS, and our republic. Joseph Schumpeter interpreted entrepreneurship as the introduction of innovations and the main driving force of economic development [1].

The formation and development of entrepreneurship theory by foreign scholars represent an important stage in the history of economic science. The scholars mentioned analyzed entrepreneurship from different perspectives, and their approaches complement each other.

In particular, classical and neoclassical entrepreneurship theories explain the entrepreneur as an economic agent who combines factors of production and

assumes risk and uncertainty. These approaches reveal the role of entrepreneurship in increasing economic efficiency, rational use of resources, and ensuring market equilibrium. The views of scholars such as J.B. Say, F. Knight, and I. Kirzner laid the foundation for interpreting entrepreneurship as a driving force of market mechanisms. Frank Knight explained entrepreneurship as an activity associated with accepting uncertainty and risk [2]. The economic significance of these theories lies in their contribution to strengthening competition in the market and ensuring efficient economic management through the development of the entrepreneurial environment.

Innovative entrepreneurship theories (J. Schumpeter and P. Drucker) further reveal the priority role of entrepreneurship in economic development. According to these approaches, the entrepreneur is the main actor who introduces innovations and forms new technologies, products, and business models. Peter Drucker viewed entrepreneurship as a process of identifying opportunities and managing them effectively [3]. Innovative entrepreneurship plays a decisive role in technological renewal of the economy, increasing labor productivity, and ensuring global competitiveness. In the context of the digital economy, the development of startups, venture businesses, and innovative clusters further enhances the practical significance of these theories. Israel Kirzner regarded entrepreneurship as a mechanism for “alertness” to market opportunities and restoring equilibrium [4].

Institutional and regional entrepreneurship theories analyze entrepreneurial activity in close connection with the external environment, state policy, and regional factors. These approaches substantiate the importance of a favorable institutional environment, legal framework, access to financial resources, and infrastructure for entrepreneurial development. The economic significance of these theories lies in their role as a theoretical basis for state support of entrepreneurship, improvement of tax and investment policies, and formation of regional economic policy. Jean-Baptiste Say interpreted the entrepreneur as an organizer who combines production factors [5].

At the modern stage, the priority directions of entrepreneurship theories include innovation orientation, digitalization, sustainable development, and social entrepreneurship. These priorities serve to address social problems, ensure environmental sustainability, and achieve inclusive development alongside economic growth. In this respect, entrepreneurship theories serve as an important scientific source for developing economic policy, strategic planning, and substantiating long-term development programs. Thus, the economic

significance of entrepreneurship development theories is explained by their focus on stimulating economic growth, strengthening the competitive environment, introducing innovations, and improving public welfare. The priority directions of these theories are aimed at ensuring digital transformation, innovative activity, and sustainable development in accordance with the requirements of the modern economy, and they play an important role in shaping national and regional economic policies.

In conclusion, this approach serves as a theoretical basis for developing modern models of entrepreneurial development. In this regard, the theoretical foundations of entrepreneurship development are closely related to its economic essence, functions, development factors, and state policy. Entrepreneurship is considered a strategic resource that ensures economic growth, innovation, and social stability. Therefore, under modern conditions, the development of entrepreneurship requires a комплекс, systemic, and scientifically grounded approach. Entrepreneurship reflects the type of behavior that can be formed among individuals. During the transition to a market economy, the number of individuals seeking to fill market gaps with scarce goods and compensate for the insufficient provision of services by aligning existing imbalances between supply and demand for goods, works, and services is increasing.

References:

1. Schumpeter J.A. The Theory of Economic Development. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1934. - pp.110-114.
2. Drucker P.F. Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Practice and Principles. New York: Harper & Row Publishers, 1985. - pp. 19-23.
3. Knight F.H. Risk, Uncertainty and Profit. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1921. - pp. 233-240.
4. Kirzner I.M. Competition and Entrepreneurship. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1973. - pp. 67-72.
5. Say J.B. A Treatise on Political Economy. London: Longman, Hurst, Rees, Orme, and Brown, 1821. - pp. 126-130.

